

HIGH MODULUS GLASS-CERAMIC FIBER

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INTRODUCTION

Controlled crystallization of glass to improve, in particular the mechanical or thermal properties, is now a well known technology and attempts have been made to extend this technique to glass fibers. The advantage of an inexpensive high modulus fiber would be in considerable weight savings for reinforced plastics as well as an extension of the application of glass fiber to areas where only metallic fibers are used due to their high modulus of elasticity.

In a study of high elastic modulus fibers Aslanowa (1968) concludes that glass fibers containing a crystalline microtexture are difficult to produce and have a low tensile strength although the Young's modulus might exceed 10,000 kg/mm². In addition, glasses which have a tendency to devitrify frequently undergo phase separation while the melt is held at the drawing temperature. Growth and coalescence of the phase droplets as described by Haller (1965) leads to droplets which are approximately the same size as the diameter of the fiber to be drawn. Since coalescence is a rate phenomenon the useful drawing time from such a melt is reduced to some few minutes as has been reported by Stalego (1970). A different approach to produce crystallized fibers has recently been described by Ashbee (1974). The glass is extruded during the crystallization process and subsequently drawn down to fibers of a diameter between 75 and 100 μ . This process, however is relatively slow, the drawing speed is about 1 m/sec and apparently the glass fiber has to be annealed afterwards. Unfortunately no measurements of mechanical properties are given in the paper. It is therefore unlikely that this glass ceramic fiber would be sufficiently attractive for commercial application.

In view of this unsatisfactory situation, the present study was undertaken to investigate the feasibility of continuously drawing a glass ceramic fiber having improved elastic properties but without a significant deterioration in the tensile strength.

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The fiber was drawn at speeds between 10 to 30 m/sec from a glass which had been previously homogenized at 1400°C for about 10 hours with the following approximate composition :

	wt %
SiO ₂	45
CaO ²	15
Al ₂ O ₃	12
TiO ₂ ³	9
B ₂ O ₃	8
P ₂ O ₅	7
Na ₂ CO ₃	4

This composition, which is quite similar to the composition of E-glass, was chosen in order to ensure drawing characteristics corresponding to those of E-glass. In order to overcome the problem of liquid immiscibility in the crucible due to the presence of TiO₂ and P₂O₅ in the glass, the temperature of the melt was such as to maintain a homogeneous glass. The temperature of the bushing through which the fiber was drawn was lower and it is thought that only at this point did the glass undergo phase separation. In this way, not only could a phase separated fiber be continuously drawn, but in addition, the second phase droplets were deformed by the drawing process as indicated in Figs. 1 and 2. The photographs illustrate that the higher the drawing speed the longer are the second phase "droplets", which are spindle shaped rather than spherical.

Figure 1 : Microtexture of the glass ceramic fiber drawn at a speed 2m/sec. Diameter 52 μ . The droplets have a length of about 8 μ and a cross section of about 3 μ . Magnification 350 x.

Fig. 2 : Microtexture of the glass ceramic fiber drawn at a speed of 14 m/sec. Diameter $40\ \mu$. The "droplets" have a length of about $12\ \mu$ and a diameter $1.5\ \mu$. Magnification 350 x.

Partial crystallization of the fiber surface was accomplished by allowing the fiber to pass through a small tubular furnace which was positioned between the crucible and the drum on which the fiber was wound. The temperature and the dimensions of this furnace were such that the surface of the glass fiber, rapidly passing through the furnace, became sufficiently hot to crystallize. It is assumed that the center of the fiber remained below the crystallization temperature and that the relatively cool inner core ensured the necessary tensile strength for drawing at speeds up to 30 m/sec.

3. MICROTEXTURE

The tendency of TiO_2 as well as P_2O_5 to induce liquid phase separation in silicate glasses has been reported by a number of authors such as McMillan (1964). The precise nature of the phase separation of this material proved to be somewhat complex. Optical and scanning electron micrographs indicated a liquation microtexture where the second phase droplets form an assembly of highly elongated spindles all oriented parallel to the fiber axis. After etching the microtexture on the surface of the glass ceramic fiber is easily visible as can be seen in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 : Scanning electron micrograph of the glass ceramic fiber having a diameter of 8μ . The fiber is etched in order to make the microtexture visible. Magnification 6000 x.

Electron micrographs reveal the presence of a much finer microtexture due to an additional phase separation. The "third" phase droplets are of ellipsoidal shape (Figs. 4 and 5) and arranged in the form of a string of pearls parallel to the principal axis of the "second" phase spindles (Fig. 4). However not all "third" phase droplets are oriented this way as can be seen from Figure 6. This peculiar misalignment is apparently due to "second" phase spindles close to the surface of the fiber which are deformed or rather elongated when the fiber passes through the tubular furnace. In this case the surface of the fiber is heated slightly above the softening point, which leads to a shear deformation of the "second" phase droplets. The "third" phase droplets take the shape of either elongated ellipsoids or spindles during their growth in the "second" phase resulting from the heat treatment in the tubular furnace. The faster the drawing speed the smaller is the angle of misalignment. For instance at a drawing speed of 1 m/sec the angle is about 50° and at a speed of 10 m/sec the misalignment is decreased to an angle of 20° .

Fig. 4 : Electron micrograph (40 000 x) of the glass ceramic fiber showing a "second" phase spindle with "third" phase droplets aligned parallel to the fiber axis. Because of this alignment the "second" phase spindle seems to originate from the core of the fiber.

Fig. 5 : Electron micrograph (40 000 x) of the glass ceramic fiber showing the alignment of the "third" phase droplets in "strings of pearls".

Fig. 6 : Electron micrograph (40 000 x) of the glass ceramic fiber illustrating a "second" phase spindle with "third" phase ellipsoids or spindles aligned at an angle of about 60° to the fiber axis.

Electron diffraction experiments made on small fragments indicate the presence of a crystalline phase with a diffraction pattern similar to that of a silicocarnotite with the approximate formula $5 \text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot 2 \text{Ca}_2\text{SiO}_4$ whose has been published by Nurse, Welch and Gutt (1959). Figure 7 represents the electron diffraction pattern and the accompanying table compares the d-values obtained therefrom with the d-values obtained by Nurse et al using x-ray diffraction.

Table : Electron and x-ray diffraction patterns (d-value in Å) of a silicocarnotite. The d-values of the electron diffraction are arranged according to the nearest d-value of the x-ray diffraction.

Electron diffraction of the glass ceramic fiber	X-ray diffraction of a silicocarnotite according to Nurse et al.
-	8.56
-	7.82
-	5.65
5.32	5.29
4.58	4.55
-	4.05
3.91	3.92
-	3.87
-	3.80
-	3.59
3.28	3.29
-	3.19
-	3.09
-	3.02
-	2.96
-	2.82
2.80	2.80
2.66	2.72
-	2.60
-	2.58
-	2.53
-	2.46
2.31	
1.97	
1.83	

Fig. 7 : Electron diffraction pattern made on fragments of the glass ceramic fiber drawn at 10 m/sec.

It is difficult to determine where the crystallization takes place however it seems that the "third" phase droplets are at least partially crystalline and contain the phase as identified above. It is concluded from the presence of a phosphorous-rich silicocarnotite that P_2O_5 added to the glass composition serves as a nucleating agent for the phase separation and the subsequent crystallization. The amount of crystallization is very low and the crystals appear predominantly in the surface layer which is sufficiently heated by the tubular furnace. No crystallization, not even sporadic, has been observed when the fiber is drawn without passing through the tubular furnace.

4. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

For 7 to 8 μ diameter fibers passing through the tubular furnace caught in flight the average values of E (modulus of elasticity) and σ (tensile strength) were :

$$\begin{aligned} E &= 11.100 \pm 500 \text{ kg/mm}^2 \\ \sigma &= 260 \pm 20 \text{ kg/mm}^2 \end{aligned}$$

For fibers of about the same diameter however without passing through the tubular furnace the average values of E and σ were :

$$\begin{aligned} E &= 7850 \pm 150 \text{ kg/mm}^2 \\ \sigma &= 188 \pm 13 \text{ kg/mm}^2 \end{aligned}$$

The fibers appear to be somewhat less sensitive to surface damage especially when the drawing speed is slow. Under these conditions the residence time of the fiber in the tubular furnace is longer and hence crystallization will take place closer to the core of the fiber. It is assumed that crack blunting by these crystals may well lead to a higher resistance against surface damage than is the case with ordinary fibers.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study shows that it is possible, using rather conventional techniques, to draw continuously a phase-separated, partially crystallized glass fiber. Furthermore the Young's modulus can be significantly increased over current values for commercial glass fibers while still maintaining an adequate tensile strength. The values of E-modulus observed with this glass ceramic fiber compare favourably with the best modulus of 12,200 kg/mm² reported by Bacon (1973) on glass systems consisting primarily of low atomic number oxides and rare-earth oxides.

By further increasing the crystalline content of the fibers, either by lengthening the crystallization time (longer tubular furnace) or by a suitable modification of the composition it seems likely that Young's moduli up to twice those of presently available glass fibers could be achieved.

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